

Molecular identification of *Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax* from Bahía de La Paz, Mexico

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Abstract

The Gulf of California is recognized as an area with a high primary productivity. Dinoflagellate species of the genus *Alexandrium* such as *A. catenella* and *A. ostenfeldii*, that produce hydrophilic and lipophilic toxins inhabit in this region. In April 2019, from a water sample collected in southern Bahía de La Paz individual cells were identified morphologically as *Alexandrium pseudogonyaulax*. To corroborate the identification, monoclonal cell cultures were grown in GSe medium, at 24 ± 1 °C at a salinity of 34, under a 12:12 h L:D cycle at $150 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Molecular identification was performed amplifying rDNA regions: 28S, 18S and 5.8S, with rDNA universal primers. The length of the sequences was 682 bp, 1657 bp, and 493 bp, respectively. Maxima Parsimony, Maximum Likelihood, and Bayesian Inference algorithms were used to perform phylogenetic analyzes. The best substitution model selected for 28S and 5.8S was TrN+G, and GTR+G for 18S sequences. The sequences of BP0419 strain from Bahía de La Paz fell within the *A. pseudogonyaulax* clade. These isolates also produced goniotoxin A (0.23 pg cell⁻¹), a lipophilic toxin with hemolytic activity, and is the primary reason this species is suspected of being ichthyotoxic. In coastal waters of Mexico *A. pseudogonyaulax* has been reported in the Pacific coast and the Gulf of California, although these previous studies did not confirm the species identification molecularly. The toxicity in animal and cellular models, as well as the allelopathic interactions between this strain and other microorganisms will be determined in future studies.

Keywords: Gulf of California, Molecular taxonomy, phylogeny, rDNA

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Introduction

Dinoflagellates that produce hydrophilic and lipophilic toxins inhabit in the Gulf of California, an important region for shellfish fisheries in Mexico that supports an extraordinary diversity of marine life, including many species of invertebrates and vertebrates, such as: commercial species of shrimp, sardine and giant squid (Brusca *et al.*, 2005; Okolodkov and Gárate-Lizárraga, 2006; Arreguín-Sánchez *et al.*, 2017).

The genus *Alexandrium* includes more than 30 species, 11 out of which produce saxitoxin and its analogs (paralytic shellfish toxins, PST), also species as *A. ostenfeldii* can produce both PST and spirolides (Cembella *et al.*, 2001; Tomas *et al.*, 2012; Salgado *et al.*, 2015), while *A. monilatum*, *A. hiranoi* and *A. pseudogonyaulax* produce goniiodomin A (GDA), a lipophilic compound with antifungal and hemolytic properties (Murakami *et al.*, 1988; Hsia, 2005).

In recent years the interest in blooms caused by *A. pseudogonyaulax* have increased. Though no adverse in humans have been attributed to this species, it has been shown to be hepatotoxic in animal models (Terao *et al.*, 1898). In Mexico, molecular data of *A. pseudogonyaulax* and toxinology is unknown.

Material and Methods

Sampling and cell isolation

In April of 2019, three water samples were obtained at a depth of 4 m, near Balandra beach (24°19'46" N, 110°20'00" W), an important recreational site in southern Gulf of California. Live phytoplankton cells were collected with a 20 µm phytoplankton net

and transferred to 250 mL flasks. The surface temperature of the water column was 22 °C and the salinity was 35.

In the laboratory, individual cells of *Alexandrium* sp. were isolated by the microcapillary method, “washing” the cells in small drops of GSe medium, modified by the addition of earth worm soil extract (Bustillos-Guzmán *et al.*, 2015). Isolated cells were placed individually in 96-well plates. The isolates were maintained at a salinity of 34, 24 °C ± 1 °C, with a photon flux of 150 µmol m⁻²s⁻¹ and a light dark cycle 12:12. After two weeks cells were transferred to six-well plates, and scaled up to 50 mL glass tubes with 25 mL of GSe medium. Culture of BP0419 was selected for further analysis. When that culture reached 500 cells mL⁻¹, one milliliter was transferred to an Eppendorf tube and centrifuged at 857 rfc (Sorvall Legend XF, ThermoScientific, U.S.A.) at 5 min, 24 °C to obtain a cellular pellet, discarding the supernatant for DNA extraction.

Microscope observations

Live vegetative cells of the strain BP0419 were observed in an inverted microscope AxioVertA1 (Zeiss, Germany). A drop of distilled water was added to induce the cell lysis and view the thecal plates at 40X, giving particular attention to the shape of the 1' precingular plate and the apical pore.

DNA extraction, amplification and sequencing

To obtain genomic DNA from the cellular pellet the Quick DNA™ Miniprep kit (D3024) of ZYMO RESEARCH was used. Extracts of genomic DNA were observed in agarose gel 1.5%, in electrophoresis with TBE 1X buffer.

The amplification of LSU rDNA partial sequences, was performed with the primers D1F (5'ACCCGCTGAATTTAAGCATA3') and D2R (5'CCTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGA3') (Scholin *et al.*, 1994); 18F (5'ACCTGGTTGATCCTGC-CAGT3') and 18R (5'TGATCCTTCTGCAG-GTTCAC3'); 5.8F (5'TATGCTTAAATTTCAG-CGGGT3') and (5.8R 5'GTGAACCTGCAGA-AGGATCA3') (Hosoi-Tanabe *et al.*, 2006), the amplicons were verified in agarose gels, finally these samples were sent to Macrogen Inc., Seoul Korea, sequencing service.

Phylogenetic analysis

To obtain a consensus sequence the complementary DNA, forward and reverse strands were edited manually with the software Sequencher 4.1.4 (Gene Codes, Ann Arbor, MI) using default parameters. The sequences were analyzed with Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) of the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), to select sequences of the subgenera: *Alexandrium* and *Gessnerium* for the phylogenetic reconstruction. Sequences were aligned using the software Clustal X v.2.1 and saved in Nexus format. The phylogenetic identity and tree topology were corroborated using three distinct algorithms: maximum parsimony (MP), maximum likelihood (ML) and Bayesian inference (BI). MP and ML tests were executed in PAUP 4.10b (Swofford, 2003), and BI analyses was carried out in MrBayes 3.1.2 (Ronquist and Huelsenbeck, 2003). Node support was assessed via 10 x 10³ bootstrap replicates for MP, and the nucleotidic substitution model for ML and BI was selected using ModelTest v. 3.7 (Posada and Crandall, 1998). A bootstrap of 100 replicates was selected for ML, whereas 3 x 10⁶ generations sampled

every 100 generations and burn-in of 7500 were chosen for BI. Phylogenetic trees were visualized using the program TreeView X 0.5.1 (Page, 1996).

GDA determination

Cells in exponential growth phase were used for toxin analysis at a cell density of 22 x 10³ cells mL⁻¹. A total of 44 x 10³ cells were harvested and lyophilized. The resulting dried pellet was transferred into a 2-mL cryovial and one mL methanol and 0.9 g Lysing Matrix D (Thermo-Savant, Illkirch, France) were added. The sample was homogenized by reciprocal shaking for 45 s at 6.5 m s⁻¹ (FastPrep Instrument, Thermo-Savant) followed by centrifugation for 15 min at 21,130 rfc (5415R, Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany). The supernatant was transferred into a spin filter (0.45 µm, Millipore Ultrafree, Eschborn, Germany) and centrifuged for 30 s at 10,000 rcf (5415R, Eppendorf). The filtrate was transferred into HPLC vials and analyzed for goniodomins by liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry as detailed in Krock *et al.* (2018).

Results and Discussion

When BP0419 strain was isolated, cell morphology observed under light microscopy suggested that it was similar to *A. pseudogonyaulax*. Figure 1: A) shows a vegetative cell, and B) the apical view showing 1' precingular plate and the apical plate complex, surrounding the apical pore (Po).

Partial sequences of 682 bp, 1,700 bp, and 550 bp of 28S, 18S and 5.8S were analysed (Fig. 2), using as outgroup sequences of *Gymnodinium catenatum*. The best fit substitution model for

28S and 5.8S sequences was TrN+G, while GTR+G model was the best fit substitution model for 18S sequences.

Fig. 1. Light microscopy images at 40x of: A) *A. pseudogonyaulax* BP0419 vegetative cell, and B) apical view showing the shape of the 1' plate and the apical pore (Po).

Sequences of BP0419 strain with each rDNA subunit fell within the *A. pseudogonyaulax* clade. Strains from distant geographic regions, shared the same haplotype.

Although sequences of *A. hiranoi* were not available for the phylogenetic reconstruction with 5.8S sequences, with 28S this species was included within the same clade of *A. pseudogonyaulax*, because only one transversion (adenine in *A. hiranoi* and thymine in *A. pseudogonyaulax*) was observed; whereas 18S sequences showed one transition with adenine in *A. hiranoi* and guanine in *A. pseudogonyaulax*, however the presence the guanine in other species included in the analysis was observed. For this reason, it is necessary to include more sequences of *A. hiranoi* to corroborate that this transition is really a mutation in this species and not a commonly occurring polymorphism.

The close phylogenetic relationship between *A. hiranoi* and *A. pseudogonyaulax* was previously observed by Kim *et al.* (2005), the authors included both species within

group III, were both taxa had few nucleotide differences between them. Authors also indicated that *A. hiranoi* is morphologically similar to *A. pseudogonyaulax*, with slight differences in the cell outline, the shape of the 1' precingular plate, and the position of the ventral pore. Another option to distinguish *A. pseudogonyaulax* from other species is the analysis of cysts paratabulation (Kim *et al.*, 2005).

When BP0419 strain was isolated, the cell morphology observed under light microscopy suggested that was similar to *A. pseudogonyaulax*. The shape of the apical pore and the 1' precingular plate agree with the phylogenetic reconstruction using three molecular markers, corroborating that

BP0419 strain is *A. pseudogonyaulax*. Moreover, toxin analysis revealed the presence of GDA with a cell quota of 0.23 pg cel⁻¹.

We will continue our analysis to obtain images to perform a complete description of this strain. This information will contribute to a better knowledge of the biogeography of *A. pseudogonyaulax* and its toxicity.

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Fig. 2. Phylogenetic trees of rDNA partial sequences of *Gessnerium* and *Alexandrium* species: A) 28S; B) 18S, and C) 5.8S subunits. Values above nodes indicate: ML branch support/BI posterior probability.

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